

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES: CHARACTERISTICS OF SPECIALIZED DISCOURSE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEXTBOOKS

Dr. Isida Shehu,

Dr. Edita Stojani

Polytechnic University of Tirana

Faculty of Mathematics Engineering and Physics Engineering

Centre of Foreign Languages

Albania

Rr. Sulejman Delvina, Tirana

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10069111>

Abstract

In this paper, we point out the importance of specialized discourse very obvious in some of the various activities/exercises used in the textbooks of English for specific purposes taught at the Polytechnic University of Tirana as well as the features that characterize this discourse, clearly reflected in the textbooks. History of the ESP methods used in this educational institution, which of course over the years and with the development of technology have been better adapted to the concrete needs of engineering students, giving a very important role to terminology and the communicative aspect of the language.

The purpose of the paper is to highlight the importance and features of the specialized discourse used in university textbooks for teaching/learning a foreign language for specific purposes, focusing not only on the terminology of the field of study, but also on other elements of this discourse, which distinguish it from other discourses. It is these elements that make the difference in the various activities/exercises used in these textbooks, making the process of giving and receiving knowledge in specific fields more accurate and sometimes simpler, and thus also bringing the change in approach between the teaching/learning of the general language and that of language for specific purposes.

Keywords: specialized discourse, textbooks, language for specific purposes (ESP), activities/exercises

Introduction

In Albania, the teaching of foreign languages in the last 30 years, but not only, has been important (even though we have some reservations regarding the recently determined hours dedicated to foreign languages). Nowadays, knowledge of foreign languages is a necessity as we live in a world where communication with individuals of different cultures is already very easy as a result of the development of telecommunication technology, information, etc. Today, the different professions we practice force us to communicate with people of different cultures, and this, in addition to the development of technology, as mentioned above, also requires the knowledge of either the other's language or an international language such as English. Professionals from different branches are required to exchange ideas, opinions and practices with professionals from other cultures and therefore languages. This is quite evident in Albania as well. The existence of this need has every day led to an increase in the number of people learning foreign languages, whether in schools or private courses, where we would first list the English language as an international language, and then French, Italian, German, Greek, Turkish, Spanish etc.

Regarding the teaching of the English language, we can say that the latter, of course, was present even before the 90s, specifically in 1947²¹ with the establishment of the Department of the Russian language as one

of the departments of a two-year Institute in Tirana. In the following years, the demand for her teaching grew more. Mainly the teaching textbooks of the English language used in the early 90s had a general character, which means that the textbooks were based on everyday conversations. Later, as in other countries, there was a need to have English language teaching and textbooks for specific purposes, a reflection of what Hutchinson, T., Waters, A²² had earlier defined in their work about language for specific purposes.

The first steps on professional English language textbooks in Albania were taken in the 70s (a few years after its introduction in the world) with textbooks such as 'English for engineering students' by Gëzim Hadaj and Drita Dracani, Tirana 1974, 'English for construction engineering students' by Petraq Buka, Tirana 1986, 'English for the students of Economics' by H.Bezhani, Sh.Shambli, Tirana 1981, 'English for Geology and Mining' by Sofika Kaba 1985 etc., thus fulfilling the specific needs of the learner as defined by Dudley-Evans and St. John²³, the student in our case; focusing on the content of special disciplines and adapting the language from the lexical, literary and syntactical aspect to the activities/exercises included in the textbooks. These elements characterize the language for specific purposes.

²¹ Fakulteti i Gjuhëve të Huaja – UNIVERSITETI I TIRANËS (unitir.edu.al)

²² Hutchinson, T., & Waters, A. (1987). *English for Specific Purposes: A learning-centred approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. f. 19

²³ Dudley-Evans & Maggie Jo St. John, *Development in English for Specific Purposes*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1998: 4-5.

Method and material

The method used in this paper is the comparative observational one, given that we started from our experience of several years as lecturers of ESP with different textbooks used over the years at PUT in the foreign language learning classes. Consequently, the materials used are textbooks of general English language as well as ESP textbooks.

Results and discussion

1. What distinguishes language for specific purposes from general language in terms of teaching and how is it reflected in the teaching textbooks?

The main difference between general language and the language for specific purposes is observed in the vocabulary or the language used in the textbooks. Language for specific purposes has the terminology of the relevant branches, such as the terminology of economics, informatics, law, etc. Specifically, if we look at the listening or reading parts in these methods, they are taken from the relevant field such as in the English language textbooks for the engineering branches we find reading passages with titles such as: 'Instructions for lamp repair', 'Stretching seatbelt test', 'Plant Co offers agriculture solutions', 'Sewage treatment project'²⁴ etc.

Besides terminology, language for specific purposes differs from general language also in terms of discourse. What is noticed in the textbooks mentioned above is that the language used is stripped of emotional colors, in them there is no use of literary figures, and in some of them, especially in the instructional texts, it is noticed the use of the imperative form, the passive one and the use of short sentences. In addition to instructional texts in such methods, there is also a high presence of comprehensive texts, where descriptions of various devices are given as well as their mode of operation, argumentative and informative texts. An example of an instructional reading passage is taken from the "Engineering" textbook as below:

- **Instructions for lamp repair.**

1. Secure the appliance in a **vise** to hold the lamp in place and free your hands.

2. Remove **screws** from the covering plate with a **screwdriver** or an electric drill. Remove the plate to reveal the wiring inside.

3. Locate the wiring causing the bad connection. Using **pliers**, **clip** the faulty connection.

4. **Strip** the insulation from the faulty wire with a **wire stripper**.

5. Using the **soldering iron**, apply **solder** to the bare wires to make a new connection. Etc

Through this exercise, the student learns words or terms of the relevant field as well as how to construct sentences, which must be precise and short, characteristic of instructional texts. Likewise, in terms of grammar, language textbooks for specific purposes focus mainly on those grammatical forms that the student will need to express himself clearly in his field of study (e.g the passive form), thereby overlooking a good grammatical part that in general language cannot be left uncovered.

We cannot neglect and fail to point out that apart from language, it often happens that the student understands and acquires knowledge of the branch he is studying (the texts are taken from accurate scientific and technical sources, which is specified in the book) since they cover the subject of English in the first and second semesters, when they have not yet taken the specific subjects of the branch they are studying, but instead doing the basic subjects such as mathematics, physics, advanced chemistry.

Recent textbooks also focus on different dialogues between professionals. The creation of real situations that students can face in the future while exercising their profession. Therefore, a special part is dedicated to the communicative aspect, since the public or students/those learning the language are required to learn practical things that they will need in their profession, in cases of professional contacts, either in the form of conversation or even in the written form. Specifically, in the engineering branches, students are required to create dialogues with questions and answers about the use of a device, or the narration of an incident during work, such as in the lesson entitled 'Safety precautions', in which one of the exercises is: 'Talk/write about: What accident happened/how it happened/what happened to the people involved?'

Below is an example of a listening exercise²⁵, taken from the same book, in which the communicative aspect of the language, the simulation of real situations in the work environment is clearly represented.

- **Listen and complete the conversation between an engineer and a shop owner. Complete the conversation.**

Owner: Hello, ma'am. Can I help you find anything?

Engineer: Yes, I'm _____ a soldering iron.

Owner : Okay. We have a few different models. Can I ask what you'll be using it for?

Engineer: I need to repair some _____.

Owner : Well, we have the Landford 250 or the Hilldale 400.

Engineer: Okay. What's the _____?

Owner: The Landford 250 is for _____ wiring. The Hilldale 400 is _____ small circuits.

Engineer: I think _____ the Landford.

Another typology of exercise is that of a lexical character, such as the type in which words have to be matched with the definitions, or placing the word in blanks in a sentence, circling the right word etc. The main purpose of this typology of exercise is to teach the lexicon, words and their meaning in the respective field. Activities of this type are given not only to teach the concept but also to enable the student to reproduce the definition. In fact, this exercise typology is the same as the one used in general language, with the only difference being that in language textbooks for specific purposes, the focus is on the term and not the word.

²⁴ Charles Lloyd., James A.Frazier- Engineering, Career Paths, Express Publishing 2013

²⁵ Charles Lloyd., James A.Frazier- Engineering, Career Paths, Express Publishing 2013;11

Match the words (1-7) with the definitions (A-G).

- 1__Crops
- 2__pivot-irrigation
- 3__flood-irrigation
- 4__hydrology
- 5__salinity
- 6__agriculture
- 7__localized irrigation

- A. Covering an entire area with water²⁶
- B. The amount of salt in something
- C. The science of farming
- D. Water applied to crops in specific areas
- E. Water applied in a circular motion to crops
- F. Plants that are grown and sold for profit
- G. The study of water

On the other hand, if we look at an exercise format taken from General English textbooks as in the example below Opportunities, Intermediate²⁷:

• **Complete the questionnaire by choosing the correct preposition.**

1. In your family, who is usually the first person to **turn to/on** the TV when you get home?
2. What programmes make you want to **turn off/over** to another channel?
3. When you are watching, do you ever **turn away/up** when something is extremely frightening or exciting? Etc.

• **What kind of films do you like? Tell the class.**

It is noted first of all that the language used is colloquial and the topics are mainly social ones. Then we would add that general language textbooks always have separate and important parts of grammar, except for some advanced levels which focus more and more on the communicative aspect. The topics used are of a general character and the sentences are of the most varied. In the reading passages of these teaching textbooks, there is widespread use of literary and stylistic style.

2. Summary of the English language textbooks used at PUT and the characteristics of each.

Almost all branches of engineering are covered at the Polytechnic University of Tirana. In the first years of teaching English at the university, the first books of English where the once of the time, often chosen by the professors, such as: 'Headway', 'Interchange', 'Mind speaks to mind' etc. These textbooks were the same with the ones used at the faculties or other branches of the University of Tirana (non-engineering one), the same as the ones used by anyone who wanted to learn English language. So there was no real textbook for engineering students, even though engineering English textbooks by Albanian authors have existed since the above mentioned year 1974. Consequently, the language used in the texts was general. Then a new textbook was introduced in the Center of Foreign Languages at PUT, called Technology 1/2²⁸, published by Oxford University Press, which, as the name suggests,

was focused on the technical terminology used in various branches such as architecture, mechanics, construction, telecommunications, information technology, mechatronics, etc. Regardless the impossibility of access to technology and the use of technology in the premises of the faculties, it should be noted that the textbook included parts of reading, listening, writing and vocabulary. Regarding grammar, as a B1/B2 level book, it must be said that the degree of difficulty was not high as it covered a small part of it, those basic grammatical features mostly needed by students who use language for a certain purpose, such as the comparative degree of adjectives, adverbs, imperative form, plural forms, etc. There was no separate workbook used, the grammar exercises were included in the student's book.

Through this textbook it was aimed at: 1. Learning English needed for the relevant professions (always for engineering branches) 2. Practicing the language in real work situations (where there were listening parts of people talking about their work in technology as well as dialogues) and 3. Learning the vocabulary of specialty (in which there was a reading part about the latest technological innovations). The book also included a CD but no CD-Rom or exercise book.

In the academic year 2013-2014, another textbook came into use at PUT called Engineering, published for the first time in 2011 by Express Publishing. The textbook includes lessons for relatively every branch of engineering, only that unlike the previous textbook (Technology), there is no separate grammatical part in it. It is divided into three levels A1/A2/B1 with 15 lessons each. The method itself is specified as an educational resource for engineering professionals who want to improve their English communication skills in the workplace. It includes specific vocabulary and contexts, reviewed by engineering industry leaders. The four language skills of reading, listening, speaking and writing are included. With over 400 terms and expressions of various branches of engineering. However, this publishing house has a series of other publications, which are often more specific to each branch of engineering, but not only, such as Information technology, Mechanical Engineering, Petroleum Engineering, Civil aviation, Electronics, etc.

Personally, I think that both textbooks used recently are interesting and more suitable for learning the language for specific purposes. Regarding the latter, Engineering, even though it is stated that it focuses on the communication skills of engineers or future professionals, we think that the grammatical part should be included and placed separately, even though the grammar, those parts that are seen as important and where the students have deficiencies, is clarified by the professors during the lesson with additional material. It is true that in the language for specific purposes, terminology is the basis and the main one, but we are of the opinion that grammar cannot be overlooked, since in order to combine technical words, terms and to make

²⁶ Charles Lloyd., James A.Frazier- Engineering, Career Paths, Express Publishing 2013;26

²⁷ Harris M.,Mower D.,Sikorzynska A Opportunities Intermediate, 2006.

²⁸ Glendinning, Eric H, Technology - Oxford University Press 2012

sentences, knowledge of the basic grammar rules is always needed, and not only, knowing the specifics of sentence construction and their organization in a certain discourse.

3. Conclusions

During the study of the teaching textbooks of English language for specific purposes, comparing them with the textbooks of teaching general English, we can say that they differ from one another, thus leading to the use of different didactic tools of language teaching.

The first radical change is in the vocabulary or language used in each of them, where we can see that in the textbooks of English for specific purposes, as is the case of the textbooks used in PUT 'Engineering', there is extensive use of terms from the branch fields of various engineering.

In addition to the terminological aspect, the reading parts in each lesson are descriptive, informative or argumentative texts, some parts are texts where instructions are given for the use of different devices and therefore, there is a wide use of the imperative form.

Since we are talking about science and technology texts, there is a lack of coloring elements or different literary figures in them, in contrast to the teaching textbooks of general English where the materials are mostly literary and the use of stylistic language stands out.

References:

1. Hutchinson, T., & Waters, A. (1987). *English for Specific Purposes: A learning-centered approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
2. Glendinning, Eric H, *Technology* - Oxford University Press 2012
3. Harris M., Mower D., Sikorzynska A *Opportunities Intermediate*, 2006.
4. Charles Lloyd., James A. Frazier- *Engineering, Career Paths*, Express Publishing 2013;26
5. Fakulteti i Gjuhëve të Huaja – UNIVERSITETI I TIRANËS (unitir.edu.al)
6. Dudley-Evans & Maggie Jo St. John, *Development in English for Specific Purposes*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1998